

Figure 1

Fig1: benzene infrared spectrum recorded at 16K after deposition of 0.5 mbar of benzene vapor

Figure 2

Fig2: The two first columns correspond to data presenting surface coverage of C₆H₆ v₁₃ as function of temperature (1.2 K.min⁻¹) and the two last columns correspond to data presenting Ssurface coverage of C₆H₆ v₁₄ modes determined by FTIR spectroscopy

Figure 3 (all the spectra below are presented in the figure 3, they are only shifted for a better read)

[C6H6_dp=0,5mbar_130K.CSV](#) : solid benzene infrared spectrum recorded at 130k after deposition of 0.5 mbar of benzene vapor used in Figure 3

[C6H6_dp=0,5mbar_16K.CSV](#) : solid benzene infrared spectrum recorded at 16K after deposition of 0.5 mbar of benzene vapor used in Figure 3

[C6H6_dp=0,5mbar_50K.CSV](#) : solid benzene infrared spectrum recorded at 50K after deposition of 0.5 mbar of benzene vapor used in Figure 3

[C6H6_dp=0,5mbar_70K.CSV](#) : solid benzene infrared spectrum recorded at 70K after deposition of 0.5 mbar of benzene vapor used in Figure 3

[C6H6_dp=0,5mbar_90K.CSV](#) : solid benzene infrared spectrum recorded at 90K glace C₆H₆ after deposition of 0.5 mbar of benzene vapor used in Figure 3

Figure 4 (the two spectra below are presented in the figure 4, the subtraction spectrum between after 2880 min of irradiation ([irradiée.CSV](#)) and before ([glace C6H6.CSV](#)) is multiplied by a factor of 3)

[irradiée.CSV](#) : Infrared spectrum of benzene ice obtained after 2880 minutes of irradiation at $\lambda > 230$ nm performed at 70K used in Figure 4

[glace C6H6.CSV](#) : Infrared spectrum of benzene ice before irradiation at $\lambda > 230$ nm performed at 70K used in figure 4.

Figure 5

Fig 5. The two first columns correspond to the data corresponding to the evolution of the surface coverage of the benzene $\nu_2 + \nu_{13} + \nu_{18}$ combination mode at 70 K during irradiation for ice deposited at 70 K, annealed to 130 K and cooling down to 70 K

The two columns of the middle correspond to the data corresponding to the evolution of the surface coverage of the benzene $\nu_2 + \nu_{13} + \nu_{18}$ combination mode during irradiation for ice deposited at 130 K and cooled to 70 K

The two first columns correspond to the data corresponding to the evolution of the surface coverage of the benzene $\nu_2 + \nu_{13} + \nu_{18}$ combination mode at 70 K for non irradiated ice

Figure 6

Fig 6. The two first columns correspond to the spectrum of the amorphous benzene ice at 50 K, the two last columns correspond to the subtraction spectrum (after-before UV irradiation)

Figure 7

Fig7. The two first columns correspond to the subtraction spectrum after-before UV irradiation experiments for benzene ice deposition at 70 K followed by an annealing to 130 K and then cooling at 70 K . The two last columns correspond to the subtraction spectrum after-before UV irradiation for benzene ice deposition at 130 K followed by a cooling down to 70 K

Figure 8 shows the infrared spectrum below

[résidu C6H6_300K.CSV](#) : Infrared spectrum obtained at room temperature after benzene ice irradiation used in figure 8

Figure 9

Fig9. Present all the data necessary to reproduce the Figure 9

The Columns A to Q correspond to the data necessary to reproduce the deconvolution. The others columns correspond to the VIMS, Gautier et al. 2017 and Sciamma O'brien et al. 2017 spectra.